

101112135 - IDERHA

Integration of heterogeneous Data and Evidence towards Regulatory and HTA Acceptance

WP5 – Ethical and Legal Framework

D5.2 Code of Practice and Data Protection Policy

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¹ Use one of the following codes:

R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

² Use one of the following codes:

PU = Public, fully open, e.g. web;

SEN = Confidential, restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement;

Document History

Version	Date	Description
V0.5	18-Nov-2024	First Draft for WP5 Leads' Feedback
V0.8	20-Nov-2024	First draft for WP5 and Data Access Task Force Feedback.
V0.9	18-Dec-2024	MB feedback received
V1.0	18-Dec-2024	Final Version for Submission

Introduction

This Deliverable provides the IDERHA Data Protection Policy and Code of Practice. The Policy itself relates to overall project best practice expectations and is designed to be addressed by all IDERHA partners as part of their own risk management and safe working practice and procedures. The Code of Practice represents specific behavioural expectations directed at IDERHA associated personnel in addition to their employers' own contractual obligations and policies.

1.1. Risk Management, Policy and Code Preparation

IDERHA has to date and must continue to follow a Data Protection by Design and Default approach for the management of risk and documentation of risk mitigation strategies. This entails the creation of a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) framework across the project that covers all the combined processing of personal data that IDERHA is planning to accomplish to empower each partner to be GDPR compliant.

The policy and code have been developed based upon the extensive risk management that has been applied with IDERHA since the start of the project. It has been driven by the conduct of a Framework DPIA which has allowed the consortium to develop a clear and consistent understanding of data flows across the proposed platform and beyond. This has also been developed in parallel with the Data Management Plan (DMP), which captures the documentary evidence and provides specifies the legally binding specification of activity and Record of Processing Activity. These processes are outlined in the Joint Controller Agreement (JCA) and Consortium Agreements (CA) on the project SharePoint. They will all operate pursuant to the appropriate Research Ethics Committee / Independent Review Panel approvals and stipulations that are outlined.

Figure 1 outlines the overall governance framework within which this policy and code operate.

Figure 1: IDERHA Information Governance Framework

The policy has therefore been drafted with reference to the ongoing development of the DPIA, DMP and the JCA. It bears in mind the preparation of not only technical, organisational and legal measures to assure data protection, but also transparency with consortium partners, participants in the research studies and the wider public, including members of advisory boards.

1.2. Policy and Code Management

This policy will be reviewed annually or as a result of any DPIA update, response to any breach or audit, or where a serious discrepancy is identified and needs to be corrected. The policy will be updated when IDERHA publishes any guidelines or advisory, including Deliverable 5.4 that specifies the operational blueprint for regulatory compliance in IDERHA AI developments due in March 2025.

The Policy will also be updated on a report from partners of any issue. Partners must inform the WP5 Leads of any issues or concerns around the interpretation and implementation of policy and Code of Practice items as soon as possible.

IDERHA must document and note issues with Policy and the Code, making amendments as reasonably needed. WP5 shall, therefore, reach a consensus on any amendments to the Policy and Code by working with other WP Leads and the Coordinator and update the policy as appropriate if and when issues are identified, or concerns are raised by IDERHA partners.

1.3. Policy and Code Scope

IDERHA is a multi-party consortium comprised of more than thirty partners from the public, not-for-profit and private industrial sectors. Whilst each of these parties are themselves legal entities and must achieve their own compliance, IDERHA as a consortium is not a legal entity, rather a partnership for the duration of the project that brings legal, ethical and practical expectations to the operation of each of the parties, and their individual responsibilities.

This Policy and its Code of Practice must therefore be taken as a guidance and reference tool that is designed to overlay with each partner's existing policies, codes of practice and conduct, and local jurisdictional requirements. It is not intended to override or prejudice those policies, rather it is designed to achieve a common view of policy objectives that can be seamlessly interpreted in practice.

This policy has been designed to work with existing policies, employment contracts and requirements for each of the partners within the governance structure of IDERHA itself, and local, national and international laws and treaties. The policy items and Code of Practice established in this document must therefore be interpreted and applied within the bounds of those local requirements, mindful that the partners may be beneficiary partners, associate partners or affiliated entities.

This policy shall not prejudice or overwrite any local requirements. Should a partner discover a point of contention between the policy items contained herein they must inform the WP5 leads as soon as they are able to discuss amendment or update to this policy document.

1.4. Other Relevant IDERHA Policies

This policy must be read alongside several other project wide policies. These include The [Transparency Statement](#) (IDERHA, 2023) and [Privacy Policy](#) (IDERHA, 2023). The Transparency Statement is a set of principles that IDERHA has undertaken to address its commitment to open and transparent operation and conduct. The Privacy Policy outlines the particulars of the processing for IDERHA Activity. Note that there are exceptions, including the conduct of studies related to IDERHA, where partners involved in the implementation of the study hold their own site-level policies.

Data Protection Policy

Data handling across the consortium and its activities must reach a high standard of protection, transparent and respectful use. This will be in line with not only the particulars as established in the study protocols,

Informed Consent Forms and Information Leaflets, but also within the bounds of reasonable expectations that data subjects and the public more broadly have around the protection of data in data driven research.

- In all processing activities, IDERHA project partners and their staff will work within the bounds of their own policies and procedures in the first instance.
- Partners must remain mindful that legal compliance is only the baseline standard for the conduct of the project and its data handling and is not sufficient to maintain a trustworthy relationship with data providers, data subjects and the wider citizenry.
- Where there is any doubt as to the ethical or legal aspects of handling of data, advice should be sought from local PIs in the first instance, thereafter WP5 in the first instance.
- If IDERHA associated personnel have any concerns or uncertainties about this policy, their roles, responsibilities or procedures they just escalate it via their PI or Line Manager.

All processing of data provided to IDERHA must be recorded in a Record of Processing Activity (ROPA) that defines specifically:

- the categories of data and data subjects involved
- the processing of that data
- the binding rules and agreements (serving as the documented basis for the lawful processing of the data),
- the responsible parties of that data and its processing, and
- the role and responsibilities of parties for that data.

It must further include the locations of processing, and the partners involved in its management. The ROPA is specified in the Data Management Plan under section 2.

IDERHA partners will declare their data handling activities and requirements in a timely and reasonable fashion. Partners will at all times follow the procedures as established in the JCA for updates and amendments to the data processing activities such as may from time to time be necessary. Any permitted data processing is listed under the DMP.

In addition to the particulars as outlined in the DPIA, DMP, JCA and CA, partners must make all reasonable efforts to engage with and adhere to the points that are raised by IDERHA Advisory Boards and any members of the public who may engage with and / or comment on IDERHA and its conduct.

- Any uncertainties or dilemmas will be raised with the Advisory Boards if IDERHA is unable to address any particular point.
- The WP organisers of each Advisory Board will provide feedback routinely to relevant WPs or when feedback has been made available.

The broad categories of data processing and activity involve data collection, data provision, data sharing, data analysis and results generation, data reuse and data management. We categorise the policy items according to each of these activities. All activities are reflected in the DMP, and further guidance should be sought from there in the first instance.

- When sharing and / or receiving data, IDERHA Partners will do so in accordance with any research ethics approvals, contractual obligations under the CA and JCA, and the particulars of the DMP.
- When handling data, IDERHA Partners will do so in accordance with the particulars of any applicable, ethically approved research protocol, and the particulars of the DMP.
- When analysing data and sharing results, steps must be taken to assess disclosure control risk.

Code of Practice

The Code of Practice below must be read alongside the Data Protection Policy above. It has been drafted to refer specifically to individual IDERHA Associated Personnel in their work in finer detail as to their own conduct in addition to the policies and procedures provided by their employing IDERHA Partner organisation.

All IDERHA associated personnel remain individually responsible for ensuring they are fully aware of and understand:

- Their local employers' procedures, policies and codes of practice;
- Any data breach reporting processes and incident response procedures;
- Policies related to handling of any query from data subjects or the wider public with referral to the appropriate Data Protection Officer or study site coordinator so that it can be appropriately handled.
- Their contractual obligations and responsibilities when handling data.

IDERHA associated personnel must:

- Refer to their line manager or PI if they have any concerns or questions around their roles and responsibilities for the Project;
- Refer to their line manager or Principal Investigator if they discover any potential contention between their employers' policies and the stipulations and policy points as outlined by IDERHA and its governance framework

When handling data (personal, anonymous, pseudonymised and / or any data generated by their lawful and reasonable processing to achieve the goals of IDERHA), personnel will:

- Use only tools and procedures that are declared safe and trustworthy by their employer;
- Conduct processing activity that is recorded in the Data Management Plan (section 2);
- Will conduct themselves in accordance with all ethically approved protocols and procedures;
- Cease processing when encountering unexpected error, responses or evidence of anything that may seem unusual or problematic, reporting these through their issue reporting procedures;
- Ensure all software they are using has been updated with all relevant security patches and updates as required;
- Ensure all operational environments are fully updated with operating system and firmware updates, virus protected and firewalled;
- Make no attempt to identify data subjects
- Make no attempt to perturb or otherwise interfere with the data in any way unless required for IDERHA purposes;
- Abide by any reasonable and lawful stipulations made by Data Providers (as defined in the DMP) as necessary;
- Cooperate fully with any audit or investigation launched by IDERHA partners when required.

When training, executing and testing algorithms, IDERHA personnel will:

- Process, assess and record outcomes and testing in accordance with specified and approved development and testing plans;
- Only conduct training and testing in environments that have been agreed by IDERHA partners, including their employers' certified and approved environments.
- Using ethically approved and data protection legislation compliant scenarios;
- Alert their PIs and other Workpackage colleagues on the discovery of any evidence of bias in algorithm operation;

- Cooperate and assist in any activity to investigate reasons for bias and emergent behaviour in the algorithms (which may include activities to address quality and bias issues in the source data);

For AI/ML algorithm development, IDERHA partners will document in clear, unambiguous terms:

- Data sources for training;
- The approach, methods and use of data for model generation and particulars around their generation, storage and dissemination for use;
- Testing and validation results;
- Decisions and reasons for making decisions on model choice, processing techniques and output capture.

References

IDERHA. (2023). *IDERHA Privacy Policy*. doi:<https://www.iderha.org/privacy-policy>

IDERHA. (2023). *IDERHA Transparency Statement*. doi:<https://www.iderha.org/outreach/transparency-statement>